

planting density and planting time on yields of short-duration rice varieties.

Ratna, Rasi, and Cauvery were evaluated under two planting schemes:

a) 10 June sowing for all varieties and b) sowing on 20 June for Ratna, 5 July for Rasi, and 10 July for Cauvery. Jaya, a medium-duration high yielding variety, was planted 10 June as a check. Three planting densities, 400, 100, and 25 hills/m², were tested.

The short-duration varieties planted later responded better to high planting density (see table). Grain yields in high planting density (400 hills/m²) increased over normal planting density (25 hills/m²) by 10% in Ratna, 14% in Rasi, and 24% in Cauvery. These yields were compared with yields of medium-duration Jaya at normal planting density 2 of the 3 years of test. In 1976, a

Effect of time of planting and plant density on average^a grain yield of rice differing in growth duration in Pantnagar, India.

Variety and planting date	Grain yield (t/ha) at plant density			Mean (t/ha)
	400 hills/m ²	100 hills/m ²	25 hills/m ²	
Jaya 10 June	6.7	7.3	7.2	7.08
Ratna 10 June	6.8	6.7	6.5	6.64
Rasi 10 June	6.2	6.0	5.7	5.98
Cauvery 10 June	5.8	5.5	5.0	5.43
Ratna 20 June	6.9	6.6	6.2	6.57
Rasi 5 July	6.8	6.3	6.0	6.36
Cauvery 10 July	6.2	5.6	5.0	5.57
Mean	6.5	6.3	6.0	-

Treatment	S.E.m. +	C.D. (P = 0.05)
Planting time	0.12	0.37
Plant density	0.04	0.11
Plant density at same planting time	0.10	0.29
Planting time at same or different plant density	0.14	0.44

^aMean of 3 years.

thunderstorm during ripening caused severe damage to the short-duration varieties at high planting density. The higher yields of short-duration varieties

were ascribed to calm, cool, sunny weather during reproductive and ripening phases. ■

Efficiency of green manure substituted for applied nitrogen in rice

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Green manure crops were grown in 1979-81 to study their contribution to the nitrogen needs of a following rice crop.

Dhaincha, cowpea, and guara were sown in early May. The 2-month-old green-manure crops were buried 1 day before transplanting 45-day-old rice seedlings in early July.

Green matter, dry matter, and nitrogen added by guara was less than that added by dhaincha and cowpea (see table). Dhaincha and cowpea saved 90 kg N/ha, guara saved 60 kg N/ha (see figure).

The combined use of 60 kg N/ha applied as urea and green manure gave as high a yield as did 120 kg N/ha as urea applied without a green-manure crop. This suggests that the green manures tested added about 50% of the nitrogen needed by rice. ■

Green and dry matter production and nitrogen added by green manures in Ludhiana, India.^a

Green manure crop	Green matter (t/ha)	Dry matter (t/ha)	Nitrogen added (kg/ha)
Dhaincha	25	4.8	120
Cowpea	23	2.8	73
Guara	9	1.7	56

^aAverage of 3 years.

Grain yield (t/ha)

Effect of green manure plus nitrogen and nitrogen alone on yields in Ludhiana, India.